

Analysis of Speech Act in Presidential Election Speeches

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Abstract:- The approach to political discourse is studied based on the theory and methodology of semantics, speech act, and textual studies. Analyzing the meaning of language in the example of political speeches is of methodological importance in the field of language semantics. Since the main method of expressing speech patterns and attitudes is the specific use of vocabulary and linguistic methods, the study of attitudes expressed through language becomes a study between psycholinguistics, semantics, and language levels. Speech in real use involves not only language but also the thought processes that occur during communication. In this research article, an analysis was made on the example of a pre-election speech for the meeting in the same rural province, by the candidates for the 2021 presidential election in Mongolia.

Keywords:- *Speech act, illocutionary, elocutionary, discourse implications, semantic structure, topics.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Identifying the discourse implication and ideas through any speech and talking is a study of the semantic level of language. The study of this level of meaning is studied as a fundamental issue in discourse studies in contemporary linguistics. Discourse is a major branch of applied linguistics that studies the level of meaning of language, the form and style of written speech, based on cognitive, knowledge theory, and psychological contexts. The main method of expressing speech nuance and attitude is the specific use of vocabulary and the use of linguistic methods based on the political situation and one's own position. Election discourse is studied as an independent form and item in political discourse. Therefore, this research work is research that analyzes and evaluates the position and opinion of the candidate through the use of grammar and vocabulary in the discourse of the candidacy meeting. The purpose of this research work is to identify and compare the meaning of election speeches and the common typology and language used by each candidate.

II. BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF DISCOURSE THEORY

Discourse is the idea and attitudes expressed by presenters and writers in spoken and written language. Discourse analysis is the study of what people say (narrative), how they say it (discussing), and the social consequences of what they say (information). Discourse (fr. discourse, English speech, lat. discursus; movement, turn; speech, speech") has many meanings including speech, speech act; a way of speaking, and speech attitude. It is an

interdisciplinary term of semantics and knowledge from philosophy, ethnography, and anthropology.

[1] In one of N.D. Arutyunova's aphorisms, "discourse is a conversation that includes life." But at the same time, there are also tendencies to consider the text as a static structure containing the dynamic nature of speech. In recent years, it has gone beyond linguistics and is widely used in journalism and politics. The term "discourse" by the German philosopher and sociologist J. Habermas was explained in connection with the type of critical discourse, such as opinions, styles of conflict, ways of expressing opinions, and ideas of the participants in social life. It is also related to the basis of rationalism, such as the method of expressing language in a rational way. It was also defined by R. Descartes ("Discours de la méthode", literally "language method"). From this, it is clear that the term "discourse" (often used interchangeably with the term "discursive approach") describes a way of speaking and speech nuance.

[2] Creating and understanding discourse is inseparable from the concept of "understanding and expressing ideas". (Van Dijk in Wodak & Chilton, 2009, p. 71) According to Van Dijk, Wodak, and Chilton, the main goal of discourse is to realize the world through language, to create knowledge, and to understand ideas. (Wodak & Chilton, 2009, p. 72). [3] Discourse analysis was originally developed based on the post-modernist view of comprehending and feeling. Perception and understanding of beliefs is a simple subjective interpretation method, and this interpretation method depends on the social context and environment, which has given rise to the current discourse theory and methodology. Post-modernists laid the foundation for many of the methods of how to analyze ideas, giving rise to discourse studies as the main tool used in the study of any social issues today. Michel Foucault, Yulia Kristeva, Jean-Francois Lyotard, and Fredric Jameson pioneered post-modernism, and discourse analysis began to be studied at the boundaries of several other knowledge sciences during this period.

The way of thinking to explain things as they are is outdated, and the beginning of talking and writing about finding hidden ideas has also affected the analysis or "deconstruction" of the text. For postmodernists, it is considered that thinking critically is important for understanding and creating knowledge. It is developing as a new way of thinking about knowledge interpretation. Therefore, the postmodernist approach is the main method of explaining concepts and ideas," B. Dagiimaa has emphasized. (Б.Дагиймаа, 2004)

[4] "The social function of discourse is to express, explain and promote events in social life through the use of language. In each specific situation, the use of language varies, and it is also wide in terms of types of communication, such as jokes, stories, lectures, greetings, conversations, etc.; topic; the purpose of the event; location, time of day, customer relations; Knowledge, hypothesis, reasoning, etc., depending on the purpose of the text form and the topic idea will create different discourse relations (Nunan, D, 1993). [6] In discourse, it is also called the concept "Frame" in discourse research, which includes the conversation addressed to the public and citizens, and the recipient parties (Van Dijk, 1997, p. 13, 2001). [9.] Fillmore's framing theory explores the ways in which beliefs are gained in order to express and communicate a wide range of issues, such as stakeholders, social psychology, and contemporary characteristics, and the ways in which beliefs are gained in order to express and communicate opinions on a wide range of issues, such as suppressing or exploiting a conflict that spans a society. It is analyzed in the framework of "goal - method - results" and explained with the concept of "frame".

From the point of view of thinking, the mental model is considered necessary to study in order to understand the discourse macrostructure. Determine the relationship between meanings and create a complex idea by reflecting on the context, time, and location in the discourse or speech. Also, the human mind, his general knowledge, and his own experience are the basis for creating new discourse. In addition, understanding the same information from different perspectives and the meaning of classical texts are studied in an interdisciplinary manner. Therefore, discourse cannot be understood without some conception of the context.

III. THE APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING AND CREATING A DISCOURSE

Teun van Dijk and Walter Kinch described the issue of understanding events in a hierarchical manner, detailing, and where to start. Creating discourse grounds macrostructural cognitive theory. It includes local and global strategies. Internal (local) strategy is to determine the typology of speech such as syntax, sentence structure features, word order, sentence patterns, vocabulary, word choice, stereotypical and unique phrases, metaphors, accent, and speaking paces, is considered a method to create discourse nuance. The connection between the parts of the sentence is expressed in detail, and the preceding parts are combined with meaning, and it begins with the study of the meaning of the sentence.

Global strategies of discourse: The mapping (superstructure) of meaning is important for understanding discourse. A mapping can be thought of as the overall content structure made up of chunks of ideas in a text. A general idea based on one of the models of texts as forms of knowledge for creating and understanding discourse. [6.] [7.] Comprehension of discourse depends on context and language use, interlocutors create their own macrostructure. This includes overt and implications, answering questions, and emotional tone. Teun van Dijk and Walter Kinch also

described the superstructure of the text. These include schematic forms, standard text formats, standard categories, and hierarchical organization.

The main concept of discourse analysis is the *scheme or model*, which is constantly changing and dynamic. Schema is an active process of connecting and filling in missing information and is studied in a top-down framework. Based on this, the scheme can be understood as a theory for the study of macrostructure in general. It may be concluded that the system of knowledge based on schematism is conceptually realistic and understandable.

Coherences are linguistic and logical methods of connecting ideas in discourse. Creating a discourse by connecting ideas at the level of meaning is the main unit of discourse research. In discourse, the order of paragraphs and sentences cannot be constructed without coherence. Teun van Dijk and Walter Kinch have extensively studied the study of coherence in discourse. Connecting devices are grammatical devices responsible for connecting discourse complexes and general meaning structures.

Theories of spoken discourses and speech act: Language can be expressed in various forms and ways depending on its purpose, through grammatical methods, verbs of object, action, and special use of vocabulary. etc. are actions). In other words, in the act of persuading and explaining any real thing, the use of grammar, the meaning and style of the sentence, and the verbs that express the action are important. Speaking, commanding, informing, persuading, and persuasive forms of communication are speech act forms that express ideas, and these are generally called speech act theory. Ludwig Wittgenstein, J. L. Austin, and others have developed principles that will be an important impetus for the development of the theory of speech. Based on the theory put forward by J. L. Austin, he created the concepts of speech. The essence of the philosophy of language is the study of the nature and internal logical structure of speech acts. Therefore, the theory of language becomes a fundamental problem of the philosophy of language and is related to the theory of language meaning. The act of speaking refers to the act of saying a specific sentence that is coordinated in the context of speech. It overlaps with the concept of "expression" in modern semantics.

What is a speech act? more specifically, it is the act of begging, wanting, promising, commanding, and persuading that is an expression of attitude and belief in any relationship. Speaking and presenting are the main methods of communication, and each act has its own approach and certain principles of speaking theory. They are also responsible for expressing the attitude of the talking parties and creating a positive atmosphere. Language acts are the most important forms of meaning and human communication, and there are three types. It includes:

- Narrative action: using verbs to express ideas,
- Attitude with modal verbs: Expressing the force and state of the sentence in the tone of speech
- Lexical choice: influence the word choice

These types of speech are not only interrelated actions but also opposite actions that express attitude and tone. For example, we know that commanding words depend on the situation, such as expressing positive tones and expressing positive emotions. Speech nuances are often expressed in different tones depending on which verb is used. The theory of speech acts was first developed by J.L. Austin (1961-1962), followed by his student John Searle (1969) in his work "How to Do Things with Words Theory", and the terms "speech act theory" and "speech act" were born. According to John Searle's principle of speech act, when we speak and present, we convey our ideas in the following two ways. It includes an illocutionary act, or any expression or speech act, which is either a deliberate illusion or pretense or a pattern of conveying one's intentions to the receiver through real or live speech. This style includes casual conversation, casual or purposeful conversational conversation. In addition, it can be in the form of a speech event (Speech event). This method is a process of communicating and understanding through language to achieve a certain result, which is prepared and planned in advance. This is called perlocutionary act in speech theory.

"J.L. Austin suggested that speech acts can be divided into three main levels, including illocutionary acts, illocutionary acts, and perlocutionary acts: illocutionary acts can be considered as the act of saying something or expressing it. The type of speech you use to express your ideas includes attitudes, including understanding the tone of speech. For example: could you please read your book, please read your book, you must read your book, etc. The illocutionary act is considered the basic concept of the theory of speech act (expressing meaning with a purpose, having a specific purpose of the speakers in any speech, offering, promising, apologizing, demanding, etc.). However, the perlocutionary act is different from the elocutionary act, and it is determined by the result of changes in the actions, thoughts, and feelings of the listener/receiver. This type of speech style may be intended to persuade, intimidate, anger, or persuade the listener to take action. It is about having an effect on the listeners regardless of what the speaker achieves or not.;

Summarizing the content above, as stated that the speech act has 3 main components, the locution device is an expression with a specific meaning or the words spoken by the speaker; Illocutionary acts are words that express the intention of the speaker in a communicative manner, such as sitting, answering, promising. Perlocutionary acts are more emotional, mental effects, etc. intended to convey the impact of the expression to the listener. According to John Searle (1975), he made the following five main categories.

Interpret: State or describe a situation that the speaker believes to be true; Command: Trying to get listeners to do something; Promise: The speaker commits himself to some behavior in the future; Expressing: Expressing feelings and attitudes towards a situation; Declare: Creating unexpected change through speaking

Linguistic acts are not only telling and mentioning things, but also often express combined actions such as acting, expressing the purpose of an idea through body language, and tenor action. In particular, political discourse frequently uses perlocutionary acts such as promising, swearing, declaring, and acting to persuade and convince. For political discourse, it takes both spoken and written forms. Grammatical devices of language are important in discourse to express attitudes and emotions. It is the principle that the basic requirements and styles of writing should also be met by political discourse.

Furthermore, election discourse is an act carried out in accordance with a specific goal to achieve a specific political goal during any political activity (Fairclough and Fairclough 2012: 1). The structure of the meaning of political discourse is based on the principle of simplicity and effectiveness rather than having a well-established model, and it is important to consider the based on tactics to gain public support, express political positions, and achieve goals. Therefore, many factors such as the position and attitude of the public and people participating in political relations, and the ideas and goals of the politician's speech are important, so the discourse will be compared and studied from many aspects. (van Dijk, 1997, p. 13). Moreover, in all political systems, the concepts of leading, directing, gaining the trust of others, and benefiting from them have always been inextricably linked with language (Stanley, 2005). Regardless of the outcome of elections, decisions, or political beliefs, in most cases, language has had a huge impact on the results of the communication process. This is a discourse study problem related to the selective use of language.

The main topics of political discourse are election campaigns, opinions surrounding elections, public attitudes toward candidates' personal and social positions, and so on. Therefore, the election discourse is a political discourse responsible for judging and evaluating multifaceted issues such as the strengths and weaknesses, ideals, knowledge, spirituality, personal development, opinions, and positions of each candidate.

Presidential elections in many countries around the world have been studied with interest by global researchers and have developed into creating and modeling knowledge. Many linguists are interested in examining the facts of the presidential election and trying to discover the factors that led to the victory. Any development depends on political decisions, and political development develops language and thinking. Therefore, Fairclough (2000) believes that "language styles and language use change with political change." Election discourse is mostly to persuade, promise, and get votes. The role of election discourse is to develop the most correct way in the election and to win by showing the candidate's strengths and qualities. Therefore, it is important to study and determine that the speech strategies and persuasive techniques used by the candidate are important factors affecting their success or failure.

IV. AN ANALYSIS OF THE ILLOCUTIONARY ACT AND FREQUENCY OF MAIN TOPICS IN SPEECH

Regardless of political content, such as election results or decisions based on political beliefs, in most cases, verbal communication has had a huge impact on the political situation and outcome. In all political systems, the concepts of leading, directing, gaining the trust of others, and benefiting from them were inextricably linked to language (Stanley, 2005). Ideology is "a concept that cannot be separated from the range of independent ideas belonging to discursive attitude", but it is a way of expressing ideas, attitudes, and opinions. In the process of the speech act, the main issue is how the candidate recruits and persuades people and creates his own relationship with society. It is believed to be related to the need to establish their own discursive approach with the help of language, use speech methods, convey some purpose and organized ideas, and begin to contain and reduce (Alan, Kate, & L. Althusser, 1972).

The general pattern of political discourse is similar to that of other types of discourse. Political discourse has the following general patterns. 1. Main topic, problem, and scope of the problem, 2. Specific methods and types of expressing ideas (proposing problems, defining solutions,

assessing the situation, argumentation, etc.), 3. Patterns of speech (promised, approved, approved, concluded, asked, warned, informed, urged, etc.), 4. Composition style (exaggeration, metaphor, narration, citing examples, proving with examples, etc.)

In this research article, We have chosen as example articles, candidates from three different parties in the 2021 Mongolian presidential election, by U. Khurelsukh, S.Erdene, and D. Enkhbat. We have selected a speech in which the citizens met with the public in the same rural province, and how they expressed their opinion using the nuances of speech attitude and how they carried out their election propaganda work. Ruling party candidate U. Khurelsukh, addressed the scope of the main topics of the speech given at the meeting with the citizens of Selenge province, Fig. 1. Shows the scope of topics its percentages in the frame "natural wealth, Mongolians, government, ordinary people, regional development, state-run factory, labor n people, people, hard-working, country road, forest, social fairness, policy for regional development, ancient Mongolian culture, renovated fuel plant, technology for proving service, a road for bicycle "government and policy, logic and shipping" and how attitudes and positions were expressed within the topics and theme, a quantitative analysis was done with examples of each.

Fig. 1: Shows the scope of topics its percentages in the frame

Fig. 2: illocutionary act of speech

For candidate S. Erdene, the frame of topics "National Safety, foreign policy, political tyranny, Diplomatic service, A democratic president, Foreign reputation, Action plan, dictatorship Defense sector, State budget, Humanity, Presidential election, A coalition government, National

unity, State pressure, A democratic revolution, Populist politicians, Birthright.

A meeting was held with the citizens of Selenge province as part of the election campaign under the theme "Mongolian people, Law enforcement". It shows how those topics relate to the state of speech acts in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Analysis of Candidate S.Erdene's speech for illocutionary act behind each topic (correlation the topics and illocutionary act)

Fig. 4: Analysis of Candidate S.Erdene's, illocutionary and its location through the speech

Fig. 5: The topics by candidate S. Erdene, the relevance of illocutionary and topics

Fig. 6: Candidate D. Enhbat's main topics of speech and their content and location

Fig. 7: Candidate D. Enhbat's main topics of speech and their content and location

V. CONCLUSION

When identifying and analyzing the features of election speeches and the use of common language used by each candidate, since each candidate held a meeting in the same region, the main top of speech overlaps up to 60 percent. Speech attitudes and the use of actions are at a similar level. The frequency of keywords is high in the first

8 parts of the speech, and the frequency of keywords decreases towards the end.

Since the main method of expressing speech patterns and attitudes is the specific use of vocabulary and linguistic methods, the study of attitudes expressed through language becomes a study between language thinking, semantics, and language levels.

From a theoretical point of view, discourse refers to the relationship between people in a particular social context. In other words, it is a method and style of communication that expresses the mutual attitudes and emotional expressions of people speaking and listening during communication or through text. I believe that regardless of whether it is based on election results, decisions, or political beliefs, in most cases, it is a way of speaking that has been influenced by attitudes and results at the level of communication through language.

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